

EXAMINING GATED COMMUNITIES IN THE GLOBAL SOUTH: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW ON DRIVERS, IMPACTS, AND IMPLICATIONS FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The introductory framework for understanding the concept of “gated communities” was provided by Blakely and Snyder in the USA, primarily based on lifestyle, prestige, and security as primary drivers. Other researchers, notably Lyme’s, Burke, Grant, and Mittlesteadt in the Global North, adopted and modified this framework. Due to the rapid escalation of gated communities, this concept was adapted to the Global South, with an increasing number and breadth of academic publications, which were not only based on drivers but also discussed the impacts and implications for urban and regional planning. To contribute to and advance the scholarly debate in the Global South, this article reviews the literature from 2000-2023 on the Global South’s gated communities due to geographical differences with the Global North. The findings attribute security and search for a global lifestyle as primary drivers of gated communities. Reviewed studies are also critical for fostering spatial fragmentation, privatization of public space, and propagating socio-economic inequality as socio-economic impacts that lead to zoning, land use, and urban development implications. The systematic review conducted in this study demonstrates that gated communities in the Global South are often produced at the expense of inclusive urban development, advancing private capitalist interests, and raising questions of spatial justice to only momentary awareness.

Keywords: Gated communities, Geographical context, Global South, Socio-spatial transformation, Systematic review.

INTRODUCTION

Since the 1990s, social and economic disparities have given rise to the concept of ‘ghettoization’, a process of physically segregating populations within individual communities. In contemporary times, there has been a significant trend for living choices in the form of ‘gated communities’ (Shamseldin, 2016) (Hendrikx & Wissink, 2017), (Zhao & Zou, 2017). Many descriptions and insights have evolved to explain the concept of gated communities, regarding what constitutes such a form of residential development for a living choice. However, all definitions are derived from the basic definition in the book “Fortress America: Gated Communities in the United States”, in which gated communities are defined as:

“Restricted access residential zones, where typically public places are privatized. They are security developments that have set boundaries, usually in the form of walls or fences, and restricted entrances that are designed to deter intrusion by visitors. They range from the inner cities to the suburbs, the wealthiest neighbourhoods to the poorest, and include both new developments and existing communities that have been refitted with gates and walls”.

In the above definition, Blakely and Snyder (1997) have provided one of the most thorough investigations of gated communities available in the Global North (Breetzke, Landman, & Cohn, 2014) (Ghonimi, El Zalmy, Khairy, & Soilman, 2013). In the Global South, developed and peri-

urban areas of countries such as India, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Nairobi, Indonesia, Malaysia, China, Iran, Pakistan, and Luanda have been experiencing a significant increase in gated communities under the influence of globalization and economic reform policies over the past two-three decades (Goodfellow, 2017). Gated communities have profound ramifications for how urban space is used and accessed. They help to restructure urban environments by changing public open spaces into enclosed spaces with gates, booms, fences, and walls. Thus, gated communities present important questions about inhabitants' usage and access to urban space and have sparked a broader debate about their potential future repercussions for urban life and governance in the Global South.

However, literature has revealed that gated communities embrace many different issues due to geographical differences of the Global South, which Blakely and Snyder's framework does not address (Ehwi, Tyler, & Morrison, 2018) (Kalantari, Rafieian, Aghasafari, & Khalil, 2017) (Bandauko, Arku, & Frimpong, 2022). In the review process, it was also discovered that there is a bulk of academic literature available which requires a great amount of time to locate and gather information on living choices within gated communities of the Global South. There is a growing body of scholarly research on gated communities in the Global South, but no systematic overview and analysis of the material has been done to place it in the context of current discussions on socio-spatial transformation. To close this gap, this paper systematically reviews and analyses academic articles (2000–2023) that investigate gated communities in the Global South cities., according to the concerns that have surfaced in studies of gated communities and how these concerns relate to the current discussions about the usage and accessibility of urban space. The work advances and adds to discussions regarding cities, particularly those associated with urban planning and management. Through this research, we will be able to consider the consequences for urban planning and administration, particularly regarding the necessity of reconsidering urban models considering the continuing urban restructuring occurring in the cities of the Global South.

The study is laid out as follows: in the next section, we briefly explain gated communities and present an outline of the theoretical justifications for their

establishment and evolution. This is followed by a discussion of the 'socio-spatial transformation' idea in the Global South. We then describe the strategy utilized to conduct systematic review. The study findings are presented next in three major sub-topics: drivers of gated communities, their impacts, and implications for cities. The report concludes by outlining potential future studies on gated communities in the Global South, as well as their practical implications.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1. Defining and Characterizing Gated Communities

In its modern form, a gated community is a guarded place that is surrounded by walls or any kind of borders to be secured and controlled by security guards to prevent penetration by non-residents (Blakely & Snyder, 1997a) (Grant & Mittelsteadt, 2004) (Ajibola, Oloke, & Ogunbemi, 2011). This place is shared by many different residents and householders. Small residential streets and a variety of shared amenities are typically found in gated communities. This can only be a park or another public space in smaller areas. For most daily activities, residents of larger communities might be able to remain there.

Different gated communities come in various forms. Lifestyle, prestige, and security zone communities were the three primary categories of gated communities defined by Blakely and Snyder (Table 1). Lifestyle communities put a strong emphasis on leisure activities. With recreational facilities, shared amenities, and shared services at their core. Retirement communities, golf communities, or suburban new towns are examples of lifestyle enclaves (Grant & Mittelsteadt, 2004). Golf courses and country clubs are frequent facilities in these lifestyle communities. For instance, major master-planned developments with hundreds to thousands of residential units as well as commercial, retail, and institutional buildings are common in suburban new towns in the USA. Prestige communities are created as status symbols for residents who care about their appearance. The wealthiest people in society live in these residential areas. Security zone communities bar visitors from using public streets. They reveal a dread of strangers upsetting local communities. In contrast to other forms of gated communities, where security measures are put in place by developers, inhabitants in security zones may advocate for and

help build the barriers.

Table 1: Types of Gated Communities by Blakely and Snyder

Researcher	Types	Characteristics of types
Blakely & Snyder (1997)	Lifestyle Communities	Common amenities with a shared interest for the leisure class, which include master-planned projects for luxury
	Prestige communities	Secured access (with or without guards) to imitate the yearning for an image, privacy control, and exclusivity
	Security zone communities	Crime control involving retrofitting fences and gates on public streets to restrict access

In turn, it protects the property rights of the residents of gated communities in combination with their unique physical features (Atkinson & Flint, 2004).

1.2. Gated Communities in the Global South

The emergence and development of gated communities in the Global South can be divided into two major categories: structural and subjective (Roitman S. , 2005). The foundation of the structural enlightenment is that gated communities are a physical representation of the social, political, and economic systems of society (Blakely & Snyder, 1997a) . Gated communities have quickly proliferated because of socioeconomic pressures working at several scales, such as globalization, neo-liberalism, and privatization initiatives. Researchers have emphasized the following specific drivers as part of the structural explanations: The embrace of diverse urban lifestyles, security concerns and fear of crime, the state's failure to deliver services like security and infrastructure maintenance, investment speculation in urban real estate markets, and the expanding internationalization of real estate development operations (Atkinson & Flint, 2004) (Coy & Pohler, 2002) (Roitman S. , 2005).

On the other hand, the subjective account focuses on the part that social actors like the residents of gated communities play in society. Thus, these social actors' goals and motivations play a significant role in the process of "gating." Both theories for gated communities are supported by prior research, though specifics may change depending on the urban context. For instance, structural reasons like neo-liberal globalization are responsible for the growth of gated communities in Istanbul, Turkey (Genis, 2007). Growing insecurity in Indonesian cities is a major structural element

contributing to the rise of gated communities (Leish, 2002) (Roitman & Recio, 2020).

1.3. Socio-spatial transformation in the Global South- a debate

Cities in the Global South are at the center of the 21st-century development agenda due to rapid and unequal urbanization. Thinking about and rehearsing futures for cities is both difficult and exciting during this intense change process. Identity politics are becoming more prevalent, and development planning may attract new supporters which has resulted from the amazing diversity of cities in the Global South. The splintering of urban space and the emergence of "islands of prosperity in oceans of poverty" are responsible for the variety of spatial forms of organization at the city level, which is matched by this (The State of African Cities 2020, UN-Habitat).

Urbanization in the Global South has drawn criticism for encouraging socio-spatial transformation and impeding efforts to create inclusive urban communities (Van Noorloos & Kloosterboer, 2018). These distinct processes are a result of and build upon more general structural changes, such as the economic restructuring of cities in response to pressures from globalization, real estate trends, urgent environmental crises, and the restructuring of states and governance relationships under the widespread impact of neo-liberal ideologies and methods (Adama, 2020). In a world, shaped by migration, these dynamics, together with local histories, cultures, and social interactions, result in extremely different, locally specific patterns of urban development, health, transportation, and transformation.

In some countries, politics has frequently supported certain racial and religious identities (Budhani, Gazdar, Kaker, & Mallah, 2010). By

seizing control of public resources and assuming roles in the provision of goods and services, political parties and other organised entities attempted to fill the vacuum in power and governance left by the government's steady decline. Simultaneously, there has been an increase in informality and the private sector (Gayer, 2014). As a result of housing reforms, private developers are progressively taking over the role of local governments and work units in residential development as well as the supply of significant infrastructure and services (Hasan A. , Ahmed, Sadiq, Raza, & Sarwar, 2015).

According to studies on socio-spatial change in the Global South as a whole, gated communities are produced at the expense of inclusive urban development to advance private capitalist interests. In short, modernist and neo-liberal planning ideas are used to create new urban areas, with questions of spatial justice receiving only passing attention.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. A Systematic Review

The significance of this current investigation is to systematically divulge and synthesize published literature on the drivers, impacts, and implications of gated communities in the cities of the Global South. The research is being conducted using a qualitative systematic review, which is a method of associating findings based on inclusion and exclusion criteria and can offer a thorough synthesis of qualitative literature (Cooper, 2017). A systematic review, in contrast to a traditional literature review, which frequently employs informal, subjective methods to gather and interpret studies, reduces bias in the search and review process and offers trustworthy findings to conclude a potential contribution to the body of literature regarding the aim of the research (Cooper, 2017) (Weisburd, Farrington, & Gill, 2016).

2.2. Search Criteria

Four electronic databases were chosen to start the current systematic review: GeoBase, Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science. The primary keywords (such as "gated communities") were matched with their synonyms in each database, such as "gated estate," "gated neighbourhood," "gated development," "gated enclave," and "enclosed neighbourhood." The search technique assessed the databases' articles. Where appropriate,

more papers were located using the book reference systems of scattered surveys. The next step involved carefully going over the titles of the several articles. Then, relevant articles were transferred from the theoretical survey stage to the body survey stage using a similar method. Finally, the papers' full texts were examined for potential relevance. Where appropriate, more articles might have been found in published reviews' bibliographies. The second step involved a thorough evaluation of each article's title. The relevant articles were then transferred using the same process from the abstract review step to the body review stage. The papers' entire texts were then reviewed for possible relevance (Weisburd, Farrington, & Gill, 2016). Then, the data from every study that satisfied inclusion requirements was selected.

2.3. Data Inclusion Requirements

To choose publications that would be appropriate for review, a set of inclusion criteria was created and applied to the findings of the literature search. Based on the following five standards, every article was included. First and foremost, the research has to be done in a Global South city. This eliminates, for instance, research that compared gated communities in cities in the Global South to cities in other parts of the world. Secondly, the study should limit its scope to gated communities (as defined by the article) and address the reasons behind, effects of, and consequences for this kind of residential development. Third, the report has to present original data or findings from an examination of pre-existing data sources. The papers that were chosen for the systematic review included both those whose analysis relied exclusively on primary data and those whose analysis made use of secondary data. Fourth, the reviewed articles were published between 2000 and 2023, because it was this time when the Global South faced severe socio-spatial transformation due to the rapid expansion of gated communities. Fifth, the articles must be published in peer-reviewed journals. The criteria for elimination of research materials were based on similar studies in the same geographical region by different researchers, either in the same or different time zones, repetitive evidence in different contexts, and articles published in non-peer-reviewed journals.

The initial search produced 80 references. At this stage of screening, only material relevant to the development of gated community types in the

Global South was selected. The references of each data resource were further scanned to cite relevant literature material, and they were then included in the list of references. A consolidated list of 35

reference materials was, thus, prepared as sources of literature for inclusion in the systematic review, as shown in (Table 2).

Table 2: Summary of the systematic review of studies

References	Geographical context	Research methods	Drivers of gated communities	Socio-economic Impacts of gated communities	Implications of gated communities on cities
Caldeira (2000)	Sao Paulo, Brazil	Questionnaire survey and interviews	Increase in violence. Failure of the rule of law.	Spatial segregation. Avoidance and exclusion	Transforming public life
Coy and Pohler (2002)	Brazil and Argentina	Comparative case study analysis of gated community types	Globalization. Increasing violence and fear of crime	Intensification of social disparities. Spatial fragmentation	New islands of wealth emerge in the ocean of poverty
Glazze and Alkhayyal (2002)	Saudi Arabia and Lebanon	Comparative case study analysis based on political, cultural, and socioeconomic structures	Private regimentation and provision	Spatial seclusion. Fragmented settlement patterns	Implications for planning and design of urban spaces
Touman (2002)	Egypt	Case study analysis of gated communities based on the geographic and chronological classification	Increased crime and terrorism	Privatization of public spaces. Segregation of rich and poor	Major blockage for sustainable development
Jurgens and Gnad (2002)	Johannesburg, South Africa	Qualitative study. Review of literature	Security concerns	Privatization of urban local spaces. Spatial fragmentation	Private urban governance presents challenges to local government authorities
Leisch (2002)	Indonesia	Standardized questionnaire survey and in-depth interviews with residents	Security concerns. Growth of upper-middle class	Socio-economic and cultural segregation	Symbolic landscape with less practical use
Miao (2003)	China	Comparative case study of new gated residential quarters within the traditional city	Social and cultural traditions	Fragmentation of urban space. Social exclusion	Transforming public life. Blockage in everyday operations.
Landman (2004)	Johannesburg and Tshwane (South Africa)	In-depth comparative case studies on gated communities	Security concerns	Spatial fragmentation. Privatization of public space. Social exclusion	Thwart planning goals. Constrain land use management
Genis (2007)	Istanbul, Turkey	Multiple qualitative methods: a review of documentary material, semi-structured interviews, and participant observation	Urban and cultural politics	Socio-spatial fragmentation. Private urban governance	Elite localities and identities are produced
Chacko and Varghese (2009)	Bangalore, India	Local and international developers involved in gated communities' construction were identified.	Luxury, exclusiveness, high-security reasons	Spatial fragmentation. Privatization of public space. Social exclusion	Thwart planning goals of inclusion and integration. Constrain land use management

References	Geographical context	Research methods	Drivers of gated communities	Socio-economic Impacts of gated communities	Implications of gated communities on cities
Sadiq and Ahmed (2010)	Karachi, Pakistan	Analysis of local city data such as census data, crime reports, and socio-economic profiles. Interviews with urban planners and residents.	Security and lifestyle	Spatial fragmentation, Privatization of public spaces. Social exclusion.	Gated communities work against planning ideals of integrated urban development
Osman, Rabbe and Bachok (2011)	Malaysia	Data collected directly from questionnaire distribution, phone interviews, and observation	Security, privacy, and an exclusive lifestyle	Social and economic segregation related to inequality and exclusion	Socio-economic and spatial challenges.
Mekawy and Yousry (2012)	Cairo, Egypt	Documentation of local characteristics of gated communities	Neo-liberal economic policies and the resulting shift to private spatial development	Social segregation. Creation of extraterritorial spaces.	The urban fabric is reflecting social diversification and increasing complexity
Yip (2012)	China	Data was collected by direct observation and interviews with members of neighbourhood organizations	Housing reforms	Socio-spatial fragmentation. Privatization of public spaces	Combating government failure to provide local public services or as a threat to the fabric of social cohesion
Tedong et.al (2014)	Malaysia	Surveys, interviews, and field visits	Power imbalances, racism, and fear of crime	Social inequality while physically expressing fears of difference	Gated communities contribute to an increasingly fragmented landscape
Al Omari (2015)	Amman, Jordan	Observations and analysis of the site visits and advertisements (in media such as newspapers, internet sites, and retail magazines)	Security concerns. Enhance the social life of residents	The economic restructuring and social changes of the last few decades and the emergence of wealthy new upwardly mobile social groups	The expansion of gated communities puts pressure on the natural environment
Wissink and Hazelzet (2016)	Bangkok	Case studies	Prejudices between the affluent and low-income people	Socio-spatial polarization	Enclave urbanism
Bruyns, Landman, Plessis (2016)	Hong Kong	Comparative case analysis for introducing the approach to the morphological interpretations	Globalization and fear of crime	Socio-spatial fragmentation. Privatization of public spaces	Development incentive
Nazmy and Sayed (2016)	Cairo, Egypt	Case studies	Luxury and exclusivity	Socio-spatial polarization	Development incentive
Kim (2017)	Seoul, Korea	Case studies	Defensive mechanism against crime and nuances	Spatial inequality and social exclusion	The expansion of gated communities puts pressure on the natural environment
Galychyn (2017)	Tokyo, Japan	A multi-case study through comparison across two pairs of sites.	Security and lifestyle	Public space privatization. Focus on exclusivity.	Determine the spatial distribution of gated communities
Zhao and Zhou (2017)	Beijing, China	Case study approach	Growing tension between the state and local government	Privatization of public space. Social tensions.	Disruption of planning practice

References	Geographical context	Research methods	Drivers of gated communities	Socio-economic Impacts of gated communities	Implications of gated communities on cities
Sara Kalantari (2017)	Tehran, Iran	Qualitative exploration	Security concerns. Search for prestige and recreation.	Privatization and commercialization of public areas. Special individual communities	No serious damage to the urban spatial structure of Tehran
Elhadary and Ali (2017)	Khartoum, Sudan	Case study approach and key informant interviews	Liberalization of urban housing markets. Seeking a higher status and better lifestyle	Increased property values	Gated communities pose a danger to sustainable urban development
Frias and Rodrigues (2018)	Luanda, Angola	Post-occupancy surveys and qualitative key informant interviews	Globalization. Security concerns. Search for a good quality of life	Urban segregation	Gated communities are a threat to ecology and the environment
Salah and Ayad (2018)	Alexandria, Egypt	Questionnaire survey with selected participants from gated communities	High-quality amenities like retail malls and recreational facilities add value to the lifestyle	Restricted access to public space. Focus on exclusivity rather than community	Disruption of planning practice
Abrahem (2018)	Baghdad, Iraq	Case study approach. Questionnaires and interviews	Neoliberalism approaches to housing provision	Spatial transformation. Privatization of public land	Spatial translation of political and economic aspirations
Ehwi, Tyler and Morrison (2019)	Accra, Ghana	Mixed methods approach	Growing security concerns. Good quality infrastructure in gated communities	Privatization of public space	Implications for planning and design of urban spaces
Makinde (2020)	Ibadan, Nigeria	Key informant interviews (with public officials). Questionnaire survey and Direct observation	Security fears and increased crime rate	Privatization of public space. Urban and social segregation	Implications for urban planning and design
Soyeh Asbere and Owusu-Ansah (2020)	Accra, Ghana	Quantitative analysis	Quality housing services, prestige, and personal security	Increased property values	Consequences for planning and design of metropolitan areas
Chitgopkar, Dash and Walimbe (2020)	Hyderabad city, India	Empirical and qualitative analysis approach by questionnaires	Community significance, lifestyle, prestige, and security	Increased property values	Disruption to planning practice
Waheed and Nadeem (2021)	Lahore, Pakistan	Structured questionnaires. Face-to-face interviews with residents	Increasing crime	Increased property values	Interruption to planning procedures
Zia Salim (2021)	Bahrain	Mixed methods including field mapping, observations, and interviews	Neoliberal urbanization and population growth	Residential segregation. Urban fragmentation. Socio-spatial polarization	Gated communities are a risk to sustainable urban development
Nazeer and Yousuf (2021)	Bahria Town, Karachi, Pakistan	Case study and qualitative interviews	Security and lifestyle	Urban fragmentation.	Socio-economic and spatial challenges
Zyed (2022)	Malaysia	Interviews with key informants	Globalized lifestyle	Increased property values	Disruption to planning practice
Hira Qureshi (2023)	Naya Nazimabad, Karachi, Pakistan	Case study and interviews with key informants	Security and enhanced lifestyle	Socio-spatial polarisation	Disruption to urban ecological cycle in peri-urban areas

3. FINDINGS FROM THE SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

The findings from the gated community review are discoursed in three groups: drivers of Gated Communities (why gated communities grow and why people prefer to live in them), their socioeconomic impacts (both adverse and constructive values of gated communities on urban cultures), and implications (apprehensions and repercussions on planning and management of cities that result from gated communities).

4. DRIVERS OF GATED COMMUNITIES

According to the examined studies, the following are the primary drivers of gated communities: The sections that follow provide a detailed explanation of these drivers. In explaining the motivations, we also emphasize the distinct geographical circumstances in which gated communities have developed.

- **Increased Fear of Crime and Violence**

Large, enclosed neighbourhoods were planned for the affluent class with either physical or digital security control measures in many African countries. Africa has had a long history of colonization and after gaining independence, many African countries like South Africa, Egypt, Ghana, and Cairo, faced weak and unequal law distribution which gave impetus to crime and insecurity (Landman, 2000) (Jurgens & Gnad, 2002). Reducing the dread of wrongdoing, led to the emergence of gated neighbourhoods in Nigeria (Makinde, 2021). They also reflected a fear of outsiders who disrupt neighbourhoods Hence, access control became the main reason to establish the degree of enclosure for safety and security, due to social polarization. The failure of local governments in South American countries like Brazil and Argentina brought about a lot of disappointment among the citizens and they felt insecure (Caldiera, 2000). The volatile situation in Karachi is usually exacerbated due to political instability and conflicts which make people feel protected inside the high walls and secure gates (Hasan, Sadiq, Raza, Ahmed, & Sarwar, 2013). Hence, it was felt to secure properties within enclosed compounds that were safe, stable, and reliable. The attractiveness of the landscape and modern technological measures for security

became the most important features of such developments.

- **Social segmentation for Lifestyle and security**

The physical features of the security-type enclaves in Europe and Australia encouraged a certain class of people to live together in enclosed, bounded areas in Indonesia (Leish, 2002). The notion of gated communities has gained significant hold in Malaysia, with the primary benefits being the well-maintained environment, ample security, and array of amenities offered to residents (Osman & Bachok, 2011) (Tedong, Grant, Wan Abd Aziz, Ahmed, & Hanif, 2014). In Saudi Arabia and Lebanon, extended family compounds and villa complexes boasted luxury for both locals and foreigners to assure citizens' safety, advanced security while maintaining the highest level of privacy (Glasze & Alkhayyal, 2002). This also ensured controlled vehicular and pedestrian access. In South Africa, the existing neighbourhoods were enclosed using road closures in most neighbourhoods for social segmentation and to protect their properties (Jurgens & Gnad, 2002). Studies from Egypt also reveal the existence of walled compounds to escape from polluted city life (Touman, 2002).

- **Socio-cultural segregation**

Turkey was one such region where, although gated housing emerged in 1980 due to globalization and liberal socio-economic policies, its distinguished types were first documented in 2007 (Baycan-Levent & Gulumser, 2007) (Genis, 2007). Contemporary Iran faces various gated community developments in the inside and outskirts of the city due to housing shortages and security reasons, along with provision for an ideal lifestyle with a higher level of security services (Kalantari, Rafieian, Aghasafari, & Khalil, 2017). Similarly, was the major driver behind the widespread phenomenon in Sudan (Elhadary & Ali, 2017). They were master-planned areas, self-contained with semi-public amenities available. To solve the housing deficit in Iraq (Abraham, 2018) the government opened investments from the private sector that gave way to the spread of gated communities. In Ghana, gated communities have developed as a response to issues with the country's property market, including repeated sales of customary land, never-ending land disputes, and ambiguous

customary land boundaries. These developments also serve to further ensure the security of homeowners' land tenure (Ehwi, Tyler, & Morrison, 2018).

- **Privacy**

A large concentration of gated communities also emerged in various Egypt (Salah & Ayad, 2018) which were self-contained and highly secured with sophisticated security and surveillance mechanisms. The migrants returning to India from the US, expected their homes to be high-quality-built spaces meant to be aesthetically beautiful, useful, safe, and responsive to their diverse needs (Chacko & Varghese, 2009). Hence, gated communities fulfilled their expectations of privacy and status for gated and guarded housing. China's housing modifications have given rise to a new kind of settlement, which shows that the majority of communities are actually not gated but just partially enclosed (Yip, 2012).

- **Prestige and Lifestyle**

The emergence of high-status gated communities has received considerable attention in contemporary times. The increase in demand for expatriate housing gave rise to gated housing in China which also emerged out of security concerns (Miao, 2003). Security in this sense doesn't mean security against crime but rather protection against institutions, with the provision of semi-public amenities for the residents. People willing to reside in gated housing in Egypt are attracted to buying a house in a better environment that incorporates locality, social life, lifestyle, well-being, distinctiveness, status, outdoor spaces, quality life for children, and security (Almatarneh, 2013). Gated communities in Amman, Jordan evolved as a need for a new social class composed mainly of urban elites and catering to the middle class (Al Omari, 2015). Hong Kong predominantly operates as a gated landscape, which is bounded architecturally, and gating is a result of neo-liberal policies (Bruyns, Landman, Nel, & Du Plessis, 2016). In Korea, the residents of open neighbourhoods demanded exclusivity, which led to walled compounds (Kim, 2018). The principle of gated community development in Japan is oriented toward the upper-income class who want to separate themselves from city-style living (Galychyn, 2017). In Luanda, gated communities emerged as exclusive residential areas, with security

(Frias & Udelsmann, 2018). However, India is experiencing increased home demand as the overpopulated centres are getting unpleasant in terms of quality of life, and hence private neighbourhoods are a preferred choice in the outskirts (Chitgopkar, Dash, & Walimbe, 2020).

5. SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF GATED COMMUNITIES

Much of the examined research draws attention to the socioeconomic impacts associated with gated communities. These outcomes, which can be classified as beneficial or bad depending on the fields they affect (social and economic) (Mekawy & Yousry, 2012) (Roitman & Recio, 2020). The adverse effects encompass the following: urban segregation, public space privatisation, city administration and privatization of service provision, and socio-economic disparities. Nevertheless, very few studies highlight the benefits of gating, such as its higher property values, improved security of home investments, and role in creating jobs locally.

- **Positive socio-economic impacts**

Many studies in Africa reveal that gated communities are an unavoidable 'evil' which provides employment to the localized people (Lemanski, Landman, & Durrington, 2008). Gated community members recognise hiring outsiders to do services like house cleaning, repairs, weeding and gardening, and other household duties, thus there are communal exchanges between them and non-gated community members (Arku, Yeboah, & Nyantakyi-Frimpong, 2016) (Salah & Ayad, 2018). Gated communities in Khartoum also have some benefits, particularly in terms of the availability of social welfare and protection that addressed the issue of housing for particular community-based groups residing in cities (Elhadary & Ali, 2017). Gated communities also improve the living conditions of their residents by bringing new services and infrastructures to the locality where they are located.

Another study revealed that gated communities are being built in Karachi on privately held property, with municipalities allowing market forces to take their course. Developers in Karachi partially alleviate the pressure on public authorities of delivering primary infrastructure services in the rapidly expanding per-urban boundaries and far fringes of the metropolis by developing gated

communities (Hasan A. , 2002) (Gayer, 2014). Gated communities also enhance the safety of housing speculation as higher property values may entail high municipal taxes (Soyeh, Asabere, & Owusu-Ansah, 2020) (Chitgopkar, Dash, & Walimbe, 2020) (Ehwi, Tyler, & Morrison, 2018).

- **Negative socio-economic impacts**

The literature on gated community frequently addresses the subject on spatial fragmentation. theme of spatial fragmentation, significantly in the cities of the Global South. As a result, the spatial transformation of urban space by gated communities often results in divided cities through the separation of land uses racial groups, and socioeconomic classes (Lemanski, Landman, & Durrington, 2008). Gated communities show an important role in dividing urban spaces, producing what has been called "islands of elite privilege scattered in a sea of urban poverty." Gated communities give overseas employees and their families a place to live a "Westernized" lifestyle free from the socio-cultural limitations beyond the gates (Glasze & Alkhayyal, 2002). In this case, the privatized world of the gated complex has produced a setting that is intended to be distinct from the conventional Saudi cultural and social environment. The spatial fragmentation in Cairo, due to the emergence of gated communities, results in a socioeconomic duality where pockets of affluence and poverty are increasingly estranged from one another in terms of symbolism as well as in terms of their physical and social characteristics (Mekawy & Yousry, 2012). This scenario is at odds with the urban cohesion and inclusivity objectives as pronounced in national and local development plans. According to the reviewed literature, gated communities tend to undermine the concept of mutual urban expansion by enabling residents to physically evade public areas. Cities are becoming segregated into two sections: one for the wealthy and the other for the poor as gated communities continue to grow.

By limiting access to already-existing neighbourhoods, public space is privatized. This restricts others' ability to enjoy their right to the city and gives them less access to urban space and opportunity. (Landman, Doctoral Thesis, 2006). The privatization of public space is often cited as a primary effect of gated communities in the reviewed literature. Privatisation of public space occurs when entry into pre-existing

neighbourhoods is prohibited. This limits opportunities and access to urban space, which in turn restricts other South African urban inhabitants' ability to exercise their right to the city (Landman, Doctoral Thesis, 2006). Due to the privatization of former public areas and amenities, many previously generated opportunities are gone, which also often contributes to larger-scale inefficiencies (Roitman & Recio, 2020). Gated communities are later built on public spaces in Malaysia, which may not have been the result of the state giving up its domination on police, but rather of intensifying pressure from the higher and middle classes for private enclosed neighbourhoods (Zyed, Tedong, & Zafirah, 2021). People in Khartoum who live near or outside Elnasr gated neighbourhood struggle to receive services because they cannot enter the gated community (Elhadary & Ali, 2017). In summary, the development of gated communities leads to unequal availability to urban prospects; the wealthy can seclude themselves in residential areas with decent infrastructure while the underprivileged must fend for themselves in the private spaces necessary for their social and economic existence. Socio-economic disparity and socio-spatial fragmentation are other themes greatly highlighted in the gated community articles reviewed. People in Karachi, Cairo, Tehran, and Istanbul believe that security measures and barriers are more than just structural components; they also provide prestige and distinction. Additionally, it strengthens the social control that locals have over actions that raise property values. These residential areas are seen as representations of inequality and economic discrepancies by residents of non-gated communities while maintaining social homogeneity within the gates (Abraham, 2018) (Hasan A. , Ahmed, Sadiq, Raza, & Sarwar, 2015). There are obvious differences between the rich and the poor because of the reconfiguration of urban environments through gated communities (Landman, 2008) which are in suburban areas. This reflects locational tendencies in different situation, including Argentina (Duren, 2012) and China (Sander, 2016). Most of the Global South is in this predicament, particularly in cases when gated neighbourhoods are next to informal residential areas with unbelievably dissimilar access to urban services and infrastructure.

6. IMPLICATIONS OF GATED COMMUNITIES

The studied literature demonstrates the implications of gated communities on zoning, land use, and urban development. City planners must tackle the difficult task of creating effective solutions to deal with the privatization of public places. By isolating neighbourhoods, traffic is restricted to a few major arterials, which frequently causes more overcrowding and extended time for commute. The frequent road closures caused by the gating of areas limit the quick reaction times of law enforcement and other emergency departments (fire trucks, ambulances, etc.).

Given that private developers are enthusiastically planning in the suburbs, therefore, gated communities are also contributing to the disruption of planning practices in the cities of the Global South (Weisburd, et al., 2016) (Yip, 2012). Local governments meet some of these demands because gated communities are viewed as "cash cows" regarding property taxes (Chitgopkar et al., 2020). There are instances where private real estate developers advocate for zoning laws to be changed to accommodate their planned gated communities (Salah & Ayad, 2018). As a result, planners are forced to strike a balance as developers seek investments from private interests and the desire for sustainable urban growth (Elhadary & Ali, 2017; Touman, 2002). The reality of needing to balance challenging requirements inside cities, such as the growing need for secure urban environments, service supply, and the necessity for orderly and well-equipped urban areas, is frequently brought to planners' attention while dealing with gated communities (Landman, 2004). Therefore, supporting the government's objectives of integrated urban development and the rising desire for privately administered neighbourhoods is intertwined with planners' work.

The lease security of the urban poor must also be protected because they may be relocated or displaced to make room for the construction of new gated communities, as was the situation in Bahria Town in Karachi (Nazeer & Yousuf, 2021). Gated communities also deliver difficulties for the functional and efficient operation of the Global South cities. Gated communities could make it more problematic to achieve sustainable urban development objectives. For example, the bulk of gated communities in Accra is in peri-urban areas, rising concerns about the long-stretch viability of

metropolitan neighbourhoods. Gated community peri-urban growth that is unchecked causes environmental harm (Arku, et al., 2016). Gated communities thus produce their distinctive spatial patterns that may conflict with current local regulations, posing a barrier to healthy urban development.

9. DISCUSSION

The main objective of this study was to systematically and critically examine the major concerns that have come up in research on gated communities in the Global South, with a focus on their drivers, impacts, and implications for urban planning and management.

i. A review of the literature reveals that security and the desire for a better lifestyle are the main forces behind gated communities. Globalization and neo-liberal policies are important because they increase the importance of private-sector real estate developers in the creation of gated communities (Qureshi, H., 2023). In particular, the deregulation of the housing markets has sparked concerns about the rise in property values and the globalization of construction. International real estate development companies are generally in charge of larger real estate development projects; occasionally they work with local planning and real estate partners, and other times they do so in conjunction with governments (Goodfellow, 2017) (Watson, 2020).

ii. According to the evaluated publications, the factors that drive gated communities are consistent with the structural-subjective theories (Roitman S. W., 2010) (Coy & Pohler, 2002) and emphasize the importance of gated communities for establishing and maintaining urban segregation and spatial fragmentation as well as for privatizing public transportation and service provision.. The results on the drivers of gated communities in the Global South resound with those from the Global North. In many countries, gated communities are said to be primarily motivated by the desire for protection and security counting, the USA (Blakely & Snyder, 1997a), the UK (Atkinson & Flint, 2004), Canada (Grant & Mittelsteadt, 2004), and Australia (Dowling, Atkinson, & Mc Guirk, 2010).

iii. For the impacts and implications of gating on urban communities, the findings from the Global South also align with geographical contexts in the Global North. This can be attributed to the

globalization of gated communities and the function of global capital in replicating these areas across different environments, which explains why the drivers, impacts, and implications of gated communities in the Global South are identical to those in similar contexts.

iv. Neo-liberal urbanism has developed quickly because of globalization. This neoliberal urbanism has enlarged the importance of market forces in real estate and housing industries as well as the elites' involvement in creating urban landscape (Genis, 2007). Although the standardization of lifestyles has been a result of globalization, we cannot disregard other local, historical, political, and socioeconomic elements when explaining the rise of gated communities. For example, the arrival of gated communities in the Global South is rooted in the history, culture, morphology, and location of the geographical contexts, which continue to form the system urban space is shaped and duplicated.

v. One recurring issue brought about by gated communities and other exclusive projects is the privatization of public space being experienced in the Global South. It does this by blocking roads with booms or gates, preventing people from entering existing neighbourhoods. This has a significant effect on traffic and movement patterns, particularly in areas with a high concentration of enclosed neighbourhoods. Because they frequently must take significantly longer routes because of road closures, this also has an impact on pedestrians and cyclists by increasing their discomfort levels and journey times. In this approach, accessibility is diminished or restricted to the point that it significantly affects how urban inhabitants use public spaces regularly. Privately controlled communities also prohibit the inappropriate use of public space or the commercialization of residential space. Therefore, gated communities and socio-spatial transformations make significant distinctions between the wealthy and middle classes and common residents.

vi. In the Global South, gated communities are being developed in focus of both new and established urban challenges, such as the general lack of integration in the city, the growing division of functions such as housing, commerce, recreation, and shopping, and the dual distribution of basic services (Mekawy & Yousry, 2012) (Abraham, 2018). This socio-spatial

fragmentation gives rise to a socioeconomic duality where pockets of riches and poverty become more segregated for their physical and social characteristics as well as symbolically.

vii. Because land prices in metropolitan centers have forced people out into the suburbs, where informal settlements have also grown, the uncontrollable development of gated communities in the Global South has been seen as a real estate stratagem for enticing middle-class people (Duren, 2012).

viii. Gated communities provide residents with protection and well-managed amenities, making them feel safe and comfortable. Today, a burgeoning middle class can be a formidable champion for urban issues, imploring governments to manage metropolitan regions responsibly and to invest in infrastructure for the betterment of society. Due to the middle-migration class to gated communities, a significant population has been excluded from the discussions on urban issues (Arku, Yeboah, & Nyantakyi-Frimpong, 2016).

10. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The present inquiry provides a foundation for understanding the drivers, socioeconomic impacts, and implications of gated communities on the usage and access to public places, as well as what it means for spatial justice and inclusive cities, in the Global South. Systematic research indicates that some negative physical and ecological effects of the rapid proliferation of these gated developments include the depletion of foliage (trees and vegetation), which results in the hardening of surfaces, increasing runoff causing flooding of the existing drainage systems, and environmental pollution. This research, therefore, proposes new challenges for city administrators and city planners as they attempt to reconcile the need for a secure environment and practicable substitutes for current kinds of residential development. Gated communities offer inhabitants brand-new living spaces, and planners and urban designers can encourage social contact and so enhance the community's overall quality of life and therefore, grow in many Global South cities.

The study concludes that the development of gated communities can be better regulated, maximizing the beneficial effects on the growth of the city, with the formation of regulations on gated communities. In response to a few scholarly

investigations, future comparative studies will be required to understand how different situations in the Global South impact gated community developments and how localized governments are dealing with this emerging urban development. In short, modernist and neo-liberal planning ideas are used to create new urban areas, with questions of spatial justice receiving only passing attention. What the Global South's socio-spatial revolution will entail for planning and urban management in the future within the setting may be the most crucial subject to consider.

Leisure, prestige, and security zone communities are the three different sorts of gated communities that Blakely and Snyder (1997) identified (Table 1). The question to ask is: are the drivers, impacts, and implications of these different types of gated communities similar compared to the Global South? Future research needs to analyze the causes and effects of these kinds of gated communities to critically offer insightful information that goes beyond the uniform analysis carried out by the research that is currently underway.

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